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Research on the Loss and Collection of Chinese Stone Buddhist Sculptures in American Museums

Liu Hong-Cai

Abstract

Stone Buddhist statues are an important representative of Chinese art in collections in American museums. Based on the statistics and research about these collected stone statues, they come from two main sources: donations and purchases. Most of these collections were completed during the 1910s, and the two major subjects of these statues are Bodhisattva and Buddha. American museums preferred the style of the sculptures in the Northern Qi Dynasty and didn't differentiate which Chinese regions these statues come from. The majority of those collections are from four different periods. Western and Japanese art concepts lead these Chinese stone collections in American museums. In the twentieth century, relevant research in overseas sinology circles focused on the style, loss, and collection of statues. It has been revealed that Chinese stone Buddhist statues are widely collected not only because of their unique art form and beauty, but also because of the Buddhist thoughts which coincide with the inner cultivation of human nature. Thus, it is easy for the recipient with corresponding cultural needs and similarities to accept the foreign culture.

Key Words

Chinese stone Buddhist statues, Chinese stone Buddhist sculptures in American museums, loss of Chinese statues overseas, Buddhist statue collections

Introduction

In the history of Chinese art collections, Chinese artworks in foreign countries were scattered mainly due to trade and innumerable artworks were lost overseas. The United States, Japan, and Europe would become the collection centers and were the prelude to the foreign collection. As a major country in the overseas collection of Chinese art, the United States has a large number of Chinese Buddhist statues in its collection, which is the representative category of early Chinese artworks in museums. The loss and collection of these statues are related to economic growth, Chinese political conflict, the increasing value of Eastern antiques, and the comprehensive development of national strength. Stone carvings are the main medium of Chinese Buddhist statues in museums in the United States, reflecting the

differences between Chinese and Western traditional art collection concepts. The investigation and research of statues are important topics in the fields of Buddhist art history, museum collection, Buddhology, and many other disciplines. Since the beginning of the twentieth century, Chinese and foreign scholars have recorded and identified a few of the statues and regarded them as supplementary materials for the study of Buddhist art in China. However, there is a lack of specific research on the collection of Buddhist stone carvings. Therefore, this paper will explore the characteristics, stages, and enlightenment of Chinese Buddhist stone statues collected in American museums, specifically focusing on the large number of Buddhist stone statues of the Northern Dynasties and the Sui Dynasty that have been difficult to identify.

Figure 1. Distribution map of American museums collecting Chinese Buddhist statues. Graphic by author.

1. Overseas Representatives: The Characteristics of Chinese Buddhist Statue Collections

At the beginning of the twentieth century, Chinese scholars began to pay attention to and collect Chinese stone carvings and other cultural relics scattered abroad. One example is the Chinese Buddhist statues lost to Boston’s Museum of Fine Arts, which were listed in the *A Record of Precious Antiquities in Overseas Collections* (《海外貞瑁錄》) written by Luo Zhenyu (羅振玉, 1866-1940) in 1915.¹ The modern academic investigations into overseas Chinese cultural relics began in the 1930s. Many works have been sorted out since the 1990s, including not only the special descriptions of the scattered statues in Longmen, Xiangtangshan, Tianlongshan, and Gongxian caves, but also *National Treasures Lost Overseas* (《流失海外的國寶》), *Chinese Sculptures Collected Overseas* (《海外藏中國歷代雕塑》), and other compilations, all of which include some Chinese Buddhist statues that were in museums in the United States. Among them, the largest list of collections is in the *Comprehensive Catalog of China’s Lost Overseas Buddhist Statues* (《中國流失海外佛教造像總合圖目》) edited by Sun Di in 2005. Chinese Buddhist statues collected in fourteen overseas countries have been verified, including in the collections of twenty-nine public and private museums in the United States.²

According to field investigations and collections, it has been found that forty-two American museums have

collections of Chinese Buddhist stone sculptures. These collections are mainly distributed on the economically developed East Coast, north-central region, and West Coast and are located in more than thirty cities, such as New Haven, Boston, New York, Philadelphia, Washington, Cleveland, Chicago, San Francisco, Seattle, etc. (figure 1). Most of these museums were opened between the 1870s and the 1930s to serve the public, and are known to hold more than seven hundred of these stone statues. The source of the collection, the year of the collection, the structure of the collection, the style preference, and identification issues are quite representative in the field of Chinese Buddhist art collection abroad.

1.1 Collection Source and Time

These collections were widely accumulated by American museums according to their nature and social functions. The sources for these Chinese Buddhist stone sculptures were donations, purchases, archaeological finds, transfers, and exchanges, which are quite different from the main collection sources of Buddhist stone sculptures collected in Chinese museums. Among them, donation and purchase are the main sources of collection of statues in the United States. For example, among the 474 Buddhist stone sculptures of the Northern Dynasties and the Sui Dynasty, 315 were donated, 114 were purchased, 40 were discovered, 4 were transferred, and 1 was exchanged.

Donations and purchases accounted for 66.46% and 24.05% of the total statues respectively and are the major sources for these statues in American museums.

Donation sources include private and corporate donations, but private donations are the main source of Chinese Buddhist statues in American museums. From the life experiences of private donors, we know that most of them are social elites with strong financial resources, traditional dedication, and modern public cultural awareness. These individuals are the main contributors to the Chinese Buddhist art collections of the National Asian Art Museum, Harvard Art Museum, Seattle Art Museum, and Asian Art Museum of San Francisco. Among the museums with a large number of Buddhist statues from the Northern Dynasties and Sui Dynasties, are the Metropolitan Museum of Art, the Philadelphia Museum of Art, and the Cleveland Museum of Art which all have almost the same number of acquisitions and donations. On the other hand, the number of statues purchased accounts for a large proportion of the total inventory in Boston's Museum of Fine Arts, the Penn Museum, and the Nelson-Atkins Museum of Art. Although private donations and museum purchases are legal collection channels, the circulation of most of the statues is complicated. Some of the sources were illegal, and some were illegally exported from China after 1930, making them semi-legal lost artworks. This is quite common in overseas collections of Chinese artworks in modern times.

Some of the statues were obtained during archaeological discoveries in China. For example, the twenty-seven Buddhist stone sculptures of the Northern Dynasties and Sui Dynasty in the Field Museum of Natural History were obtained from the Blackstone Expedition from 1908 to 1910. Carl Whiting Bishop (1881-1942) came to China to collect Chinese artworks from 1915 to 1916. Among them, five statues in the National Asian Art Museum were purchased under the guidance of his inspection team. The five statues of Buddha and Bodhisattva from the Elephant Chapel in Jingchuan County, Gansu Province, in the Harvard Art Museum were collected illegally by the first Fogg Expedition to China from 1923 to 1924.

The higher authorities of American museums sometimes allocate collections according to the nature and needs of each museum. For example, *the Hand of Buddha* in the Asian Art Museum of San Francisco was transferred from the Fine Arts Museums of San Francisco, and both museums belong to the City of San Francisco. A piece of Buddhist stone statue of the Northern Dynasties and Sui Dynasty comes from a collection at the Smithsonian National Museum of

Natural History. However, most museums in the United States are private museums and generally do not donate to each other but can exchange their collections. In addition, museums can gain artworks through exchanges with antique dealers, which was the case for a Buddhist stone statue of the Sui Dynasty.

The collecting of Chinese Buddhist stone sculptures in American museums has continued from the second half of the nineteenth century to the present, with the period from the beginning of the twentieth century to the 1960s being the main collection period. For example, the time frame when 467 Buddhist stone carvings from the Northern and Sui Dynasties were collected is clear. Among them, the earliest collection is the stele about Buddha stories at Yale University donated by private donors in 1879. Other acquisitions include 33 statues collected from 1900 to 1909, 113 from 1910 to 1919, 54 from 1920 to 1929, 39 from 1930 to 1939, 74 from 1940 to 1949, 33 from 1950 to 1959, 66 from 1960 to 1969, and 54 from 1970 to 2012. It can be seen that the collection of Buddhist stone statues from the Northern Dynasties and Sui Dynasty was the largest in the first decade of the twentieth century, accounting for 20.5% of the total, which was also the peak of the collection of Chinese Buddhist stone sculptures.

1.2 Style Preferences and Collection Structure

The quantity and quality of statues in each collection directly affect the level of activities and social benefits of the museum. From the late nineteenth century to the first half of the twentieth century, with the continuous expansion of overseas markets, antique dealers in Beijing, Weifang, Shandong, and other cities exclusively imitated the back-screen and round sculptures of the Northern, Sui, and Tang dynasties praised by overseas collectors and making huge profits. For example, the American collector Charles Lang Freer (1856-1919) said in 1910 "in the art market, imitations are ubiquitous", which is the biggest challenge faced by Chinese art collectors.³

Okakura Tenshin (1863-1913), the director of the Asia Department of Boston's Museum of Fine Arts, visited Beijing, Luoyang, Xi'an, and other places in China twice from 1911 to 1912. To "explore the representative collection of oriental art in the West",⁴ he bought Buddhist stone statues and other such artworks by using the Special Chinese and Japanese Fund. This filled a large gap in the collection of Chinese Buddhist art in Boston's Museum of Fine Arts. Style is the representative aspect presented in the unity of content and form, and the core of nationality is to observe and

express with national spirit. Chinese Buddhist statues had already appeared in the Han Dynasty, and nationalization, especially the localization of facial expressions and clothing styles, was an important feature in its early dissemination. This is an inevitable adjustment made by foreign Buddhism based on people's acceptance characteristics because the spreading of and reverence for Buddhism required "understanding Buddhism through scriptures, and using images to show the truth (賴經聞佛, 藉像錶真)".⁵ The description of statues is related to the respect of the viewers, as otherwise Buddha statues were originally barbaric, simple, and humble, and were not well respected.⁶

The art style of the times is the refinement and significant representation of the spirit of that period. It is not only the main basis for the identification of the age of Buddhist statues but also directly affects the evaluation of their value. Richard Eugene Fuller (1897-1976), the founder of the Seattle Art Museum, clearly pointed out that the standard of the art collection is to collect authentic works of art that represent the time and culture to which they belong.⁷ The identification of the age of Chinese Buddhist stone statues in American museums may have some mistakes but are still solid overall. The collections of Chinese Buddhist statues in Boston's Museum of Fine Arts, the Metropolitan Museum of Art, the National Asian Art Museum, and the Asian Art Museum of San Francisco are quite exemplary and systematic.

Through the investigation, research, and statistics of the Buddhist stone sculptures of the Sui and Tang dynasties in American museums, it is known that these collections have two major characteristics. One is that the subject matter prefers Bodhisattva statues, and the other favors the Northern Qi-style statues. For example, it is known that 496 Buddhist stone sculptures of the Northern Dynasties and the Sui Dynasty have been collected in 38 American museums, including 212 Bodhisattva statues and 148 Buddha statues, accounting for 50.24% and 35.07% of the total number of statues; there are also statues of disciples, warriors, beasts, etc. Bodhisattva statues are more secular than Buddha statues and are mainly from the late Northern Wei Dynasty, the Northern Qi Dynasty, and the Tang Dynasty. Among the Buddhist stone sculptures of the Northern Dynasties and the Sui Dynasty, the statues of Buddhas and Bodhisattvas in Henan in the late Northern Wei Dynasty, the statues of Buddhas and Bodhisattvas in Hebei in the Northern Qi Dynasty, and the statues of Bodhisattvas in Shaanxi in the Sui Dynasty are quite exquisite. In particular, the style of stone statues in the Northern Qi Dynasty is subdued, introverted, round, and rigid, emphasizing the depiction

of the body, which is a familiar concept in portraying artistic beauty in Western art.

For example, the *Standing Bodhisattvas*, collected by the Penn Museum, is made of limestone, 73.6cm high, and has a combination of seven standing statues. There are different opinions on the exact age of this statue.⁸ According to the Bodhisattva's straight skirt, the figure of apsara adorned mandorla is a typical Northern Qi Dynasty statue, the shape of the legs of the shorter Bodhisattva can be seen in Handan of the Northern Qi Dynasty, and the combination of statues with the same theme can be found in the Hebei statue.⁹ Thus, it can be concluded that the statue is a Bodhisattva statue of the Northern Qi Dynasty in Hebei, not the Ming Dynasty statue currently identified by the Penn Museum. The regional identification of Chinese Buddhist statues in collections in the United States is relatively weak, which indicates that Chinese research on the age of Chinese Buddhist statues is more in-depth than the research on regional styles in academic circles in the United States.

2. Centennial Microcosm: The Lost and Collected Stages of Chinese Buddhist Stone Statues

Based on the quality, quantity, and loss channels of Chinese Buddhist statues collected by American museums from the second half of the nineteenth century to the 1960s, the collection of Chinese Buddhist statues in American museums can be roughly divided into four stages: initial formation, developmental, peak, and stable periods.

2.1 The Beginning: Samuel Wells Williams's Donation

The first half of the nineteenth century, due to the lack of fine Chinese art in the West, was generally regarded as unproductive. Beginning in the 1830s, American missionaries mastered Chinese language, art, Buddhism, and other cultural skills to communicate, allowing them to spread Western learning to the East and Eastern Learning to the West. Missionary and sinologist Samuel Wells Williams (1812-1884) was the first to collect Chinese Buddhist stone sculptures for American museums.

Williams arrived at the Guangzhou Mission Station of the American Board of Commissioners for Foreign Missions in 1833 and lived in China until 1876. He actively promoted the development of missionary work and participated in negotiating and signing the Treaty of Tianjin in the eighth year of Xianfeng in the Qing Dynasty (1858). Williams proposed the freedom of missionary clause in which foreigners could travel, do

Figure 2. Unknown, *Buddhist Votive Stele* (front and back), 550-75 C.E., gray limestone, 208.3×66×20.3cm, 544.32kg, New Haven, CT, Yale University Art Gallery. Photograph: ©Yale University Art Gallery (artgallery.yale.edu).

business, and preach in mainland China. For example, priests from the United States, France, and other countries occupied temples in 1864, and there was a golden statue in the temple where Williams was located.¹⁰ It led to foreign antique dealers, collectors, museum agents, etc. being able to visit China and collect Buddhist statues. He also advocated for funds to start schools and indemnity funds for student assistance.

Williams's research on China is quite abundant, such as *The Middle Kingdom: a Survey of the Geography, Government, Education, Social Life, Arts, Religion, etc. of the Chinese Empire and its Inhabitants* published in 1848, which comprehensively introduced the history and current situation of China; the book was republished in 1883, and the goal was to wash away the strange and inexplicable impressions that foreign countries generally imposed on the Chinese people and their civilization. In 1877, Yale University took the lead in offering sinology lectures in the United States and hired Williams, who resigned and returned to China in 1876 as the first professor of sinology. In 1879, Williams pointed out in his book *Chinese Immigration* the summary manner in which the courts of California converted the Chinese into Indians when it was desired to bring a law to bear against them, and has a taste of the grotesque in it: "It equalized all the qualities of industry, prudence, skill, learning, invention, and whatever gives security to life and property among mankind, with the instincts and habits of a hunter and a nomad."¹¹ He directly suppressed the prejudice against China that had swept Congress, and he also knew diligence was not only common to Christianity, Buddhism, and Confucianism but also to modern thought.

In the Yale University Art Gallery, there are Buddhist statues, porcelain, and other Chinese art collections. Among them, the stele of the story of the Buddha in the Northern Qi Dynasty (figure 2), is divided into three sections. The middle section mainly shows the plot of the king's hair tied to the tree. An ascetic monk asked for his head to test his piety. The king acquiesced and tied his hair to a tree to strengthen his ambition. Williams had been devoutly and diligently working for the spread of Protestantism in China throughout his life. This collection shows that he initially regarded Buddhism as a pagan religion and later turned to a deep understanding and resonance of the core of Buddhist thought.

2.2 Formation: Collection and Research

In the second half of the nineteenth century, the Japanese style was popular in Europe and the United States. East Asian collections in the United States focused on Japa-

nese art, and American museums were able to collect Chinese Buddhist statues in Japan. In 1895, Boston's Museum of Fine Arts used general funds to buy five Buddhist paintings from the series of *The Five Hundred Luohans* (《五百羅漢圖》) from the Southern Song Dynasty of China from the Daitoku-ji temple in Kyoto, Japan, *Pilgrims Offering Treasures to Loans* (《受胡輪驢》), *The Transfiguration of a Luohan* (《雲中示現》), *Luohans Bestowing Alms on Suffering Human Beings* (《施財貧者》), *Luohans in a Bamboo Grove Receiving Offerings* (《竹林致琛》), and *Luohans Watching the Distribution of the Relics* (《觀舍利光》). In 1897, the East Asian Art Auction was held in Boston, Massachusetts. Art exhibitions and auctions were the main ways for East Asian art to spread in Europe and America in the second half of the nineteenth century, which then promoted in-depth research and public appreciation.

In particular, the Boxer Rebellion incident from 1899 to 1900 triggered large-scale looting of spoils by foreign troops, and the Siege of the International Legations in 1900 directly led to the loss of a large number of Chinese art treasures overseas. In the first ten years of the twentieth century, foreign explorers came in droves. Chinese Buddhist grottoes and single statue remains were continuously discovered and made public. Foreign expedition teams conducted archaeological excavations, field collections, and acquisitions of Buddhist statues in western China and other regions.

In the early twentieth century, the study of Chinese Buddhist art overseas was started, and scholars at home and abroad began to examine Buddhist relics with scientific methods and classify them to establish a doctrinal system. As the origins of Japanese Buddhist statuary were traced, the focus of East Asian art collecting in the United States shifted to Chinese art. The Japanese collector Takahashi Taika, who had come to China to collect Chinese artworks at the time, wrote the article "On the Collection of Ancient Chinese Artworks" in 1913 and pointed out that "Subsequently, both interest and research progressed significantly, and archaeologists and connoisseurs of curiosity and exploration became enthusiastic and traced back to China, eventually finding that the source of the United States and Japanese art craftsmanship was in China, and focused their attention on China. So the central point has recently shifted away from Japan and toward China."¹²

In the collection of East Asian Buddhist statues and artworks, the interest of Europeans and Americans shifted from small sculptures to the Buddhist art of the Kamakura and Nara periods in Japan to the solemn and exquisite Buddhist art of China. Japanese Buddhist sculptures in the Asuka Period were influenced by the

Buddhist statues of the Northern Wei Dynasty; the early Hakuho Period was influenced by the statue styles of the Northern Qi and Northern Zhou dynasties, and the later period was influenced by the characteristics of Buddhist statues in the Sui and Tang dynasties. Ancient Buddhist statues from the Northern Dynasties and Sui Dynasties were widely admired in the East Asian art market. With Japanese antiques dealers holding auctions of Chinese art in Boston and New York, the collection of Chinese Buddhist statues in American museums started to form.

2.3 The Peak: the Formation of the Chain of Flow and Storage

The international market for Chinese artworks shifted from Europe to the United States due to the outbreak of World War I. The 1910s were the golden age of East Asian art collections in the United States.¹³ The collection of Chinese Buddhist stone statues reached its peak, forming a complete chain of loss to the American market. The chain of circulation and possession was composed of Chinese collectors, international antique dealers, American collectors, American museums, and East Asian art historians with close relationships and blurred boundaries. The key link was the supply and demand of antique dealers and collectors.

When the Revolution of 1911 broke out, the collections of the royal family and ministers were scattered and lost, sold by illegal traders, and international antique dealers colluded to buy and sell them. American museum agents inspected and collected them, and American collectors solicited purchases, resulting in the loss of countless Chinese artworks overseas. There are quite a lot of Buddhist stone statues among them, and as Luo Zhenyu said, “The place with the richest stone carvings in ancient and modern times in my country is called Shanzuo (山左), Guanzhong (關中), and Zhongzhou (中州). People who hunt for profit tend to go together. I have heard officials of duties say that Ancient objects transported from Zhongzhou to commercial ports are worth millions, mainly inscriptions tablets and stone carving statues.”¹⁴

The sources of Chinese Buddhist stone statues collected in American museums mainly come from the remains of the Yungang, Longmen, Gongxian, Tianlongshan, and Xiangtangshan caves in northern China, and Duanfang (端方) collected a large number of original large-scale stone carvings. The *Tao Zhai Collection of Stones* (《陶齋藏石記》) published in 1909 included a total of six hundred fifty pieces of stone carvings in the collection. After he was murdered in Zizhou (資州), Sichuan Province in November 1911,

most of the Buddhist images were lost to Boston’s Museum of Fine Arts, the Penn Museum, Nelson-Atkins Museum of Art, Metropolitan Museum of Art, the Smithsonian’s National Museum of Asian Art, etc. One example is the *Standing Amitabha Trinity worshipped* by monk Sengxin (僧欣) in the twenty-third year of Taihe in the Northern Wei Dynasty (499), which was collected by the Cleveland Museum of Art (figure 3). According to the artistic style, this standing Buddha should have been carved in Dingzhou (定州), Hebei Province, in the late Northern Wei Dynasty. Through the regional identification of Buddhist stone statues of the Northern Dynasties and Sui Dynasties in American museums, it can be known that there are several statues from Shandong, Shaanxi, Henan, Hebei, and Shanxi.

In the 1910s, New York became the auction center for East Asian artworks, and the number of auctions of Chinese artworks reached its peak; for example, there were as many as thirty auctions of Chinese artworks in New York.¹⁵ According to the *American Art Auction Catalogs 1785-1942*, the number of Chinese art auctions in 1914 exceeded that of Japanese art auctions.¹⁶ During this period, American museums and collectors continued to increase their collections of Chinese art. In other words, the focus of East Asian art collections in the United States shifted from Japanese art to Chinese art in the 1910s, and Chinese art began to take root in the cultural soil of the United States.

2.4 Steady: Loss and Collection of Fluctuating Changes

From the 1920s to the 1960s, overall statue collection was relatively stable. With the outbreak of the economic crisis in the United States and the enactment of the Chinese government’s cultural relics protection laws, the number of Chinese Buddhist statues lost to the United States decreased. In 1930, the government of the Republic of China promulgated Article 14 of the Antiquities Preservation Law (《古物保存法》), announcing that all antiquities on the land belong to the state; the national government promulgated and implemented the new “Regulations on Temple Registration” and the forms in 1936. With the enactment of the Chinese government’s cultural relics protection laws, the number of Chinese Buddhist statues lost to the West was greatly reduced, but these losses still occurred. For example, in 1935, *Continent News* published a story about the theft of a mysterious Buddha statue.¹⁷

From the 1940s to the early 1960s, the development of the collections of Chinese Buddhist statues in American museums regained momentum. In 1941, the

Figure 3. *Standing Amitabha Trinity* Gray limestone. H. 94.6cm. The Cleveland Museum of Art. 1959.130, Photograph: ©Cleveland Museum of Art (www.clevelandart.org).

United States confiscated all Chinese and other Far Eastern artworks from the American branch of the Yamanaka Chamber of Commerce and publicly auctioned them off. The collection of Chinese Buddhist statues in Western museums continued to flourish, and the collection of Buddhist statues became systematic. Western museums, especially large Asian art museums such as the Asian Art Museum of San Francisco, had a wide variety of Chinese Buddhist statues. After 1970, the collections of Chinese Buddhist statues in American museums decreased significantly. Chinese Buddhist statues in American museums were representative, reflecting the development of the modern American economy and multiculturalism. Since the late nineteenth century, the collection and research of Chinese Buddhist statues in the West continued to develop in depth along with the understanding of the form and connotation of Buddhist statues.

On the whole, before the 1970s, the collection of Chinese Buddhist stone statues in American museums had a complicated circulation process. The focus was on the collection, due to the translation characteristics of heterogeneous cultures, the reception of statues was biased towards form, and the understanding of meaning was slow; the research on identification was weak. Since the late twentieth century, the study of Chinese Buddhist statues in American museums has continued to deepen, and important developments have been made in the study of individual portraits and great collectors, catalog publishing, and digital construction. Museums serve the needs of the multicultural development of American society and offer novel and rich displays, exhibitions, publishing, and other activities that give full play to the social benefits of museums. The loss of Chinese art in modern times is the misery of Chinese culture. The exhibition of Chinese Buddhist stone statues in American museums has objectively enhanced the overseas influence of Chinese art.

3. Convergence of Ideas: Concept of Chinese Buddhist Stone Statue Collection

The collector's knowledge and taste in Chinese art determines the selection of pieces for collections. For American collectors and museum personnel in the first half of the twentieth century, the collection of Chinese ceramics had begun centuries before, while Chinese Buddhist stone statues were a new field where it was difficult to judge the authenticity and value. The key to collecting lies in knowing what is precious. At the end of the nineteenth century and the beginning of the twentieth century, the focus of East Asian art collections

in the United States shifted from Japanese art to Chinese Buddhist statues. Western and Japanese traditional art collection concepts show the importance and essence of Chinese Buddhist stone sculptures and point out the direction of collection for American museums.

In traditional Chinese art, Buddhist sculpture and Buddhist painting share a common philosophy, subject matter, and expression but are not revered by the literati and are not part of traditional mainstream art. In Western and Japanese art, on the other hand, sculpture is as important as painting, and stone sculpture is regarded as a significant part of fine art. Ancient Greek sculpture became classic with its noble purity and quiet greatness. The scholar Stanley K. Abe talked about the driving reason for American society's interest in Chinese sculpture. Archaeology has uncovered wonderful sculptures, and in Western philosophy, ancient Greek and Roman sculpture symbolize the beauty of the ideal art.¹⁸ The art of Chinese stone carving has been seriously lost.

Buddhism is revered, and Buddhist statues are protected in Japan. The solemn and exquisite Buddhist sculptures are a significant part of Japanese traditional art, and are well-known and understood works of art. Tracing back to the origin of ancient Japanese art, the focus of East Asian art collections in the United States shifted from Japanese art to Chinese Buddhist statues. Ernest F. Fenollosa (1853-1908) of Boston's Museum of Fine Arts, Okakura Tenshin, Freer, and others led the collection of early Chinese Buddhist art in the United States.

In 1878, Fenollosa became a professor of political science, economics, and philosophy at Tokyo Imperial University, where he also studied and acquired Japanese and Chinese art. In his book *The Origin of Chinese and Japanese Art*, he elaborates on the beauty of China's special cultural circle and its internal structure, stating "How profoundly Chinese and Japanese civilization in general, and art in particular, were gradually transformed by this quiet, pungent influence, has never been written by any native scholar, and hardly even conceived by any European".¹⁹ In 1890, he moved from Tokyo, Japan, back to Boston, Massachusetts in the United States, and became the first head of the Oriental Department of Boston's Museum of Fine Arts, promoting the collection of Chinese Buddhist art. The Japanese-style appreciation model he guided established the Western standard of Asian art, influenced the taste of East Asian art in American museums, and influenced many collectors and artists such as Okakura Tenshin, Freer, and Whistler.

Okakura Tenshin is the pioneer of Japanese modern art and the disseminator of Eastern art to the West. He

wrote that Asian Buddhist art has a similar status to ancient Greek art, which laid the foundation for the development and dissemination of later art.²⁰ At a time when international circulation of Japanese art was declining and many Chinese works of art were being sold, he pushed Boston's Museum of Fine Arts to shift its East Asian art collection to Chinese art. In 1910, he served as the Director of the Asian Department of Boston's Museum of Fine Arts, acquiring Chinese art through a special Sino-Japanese fund. He visited China several times from 1893 to 1912, buying antiques in Beijing, Luoyang, and Xi'an. Some are recorded in "Kyushu China Travel Diary" and "China-Japan Art New Collection Exhibition". He also purchased through Hayasaki Kokichi (1874-1956), who lived in China for a long time, Chinese sculptures and paintings, such as the stone-carved *Statue of the Heavenly King* from the Tang Dynasty at Xiangji Temple (香積寺) in Xi'an, Shaanxi Province in 1910, filling a gap in the collection of Chinese Buddhist art in Boston's Museum of Fine Arts.

American and European collectors discovered the unique beauty of Chinese Buddhist stone statues. They knew that the relics were throughout China and that the collections of major Chinese collectors were lost. In addition, the overseas supply of Japanese art declined due to ancient shrine protection laws.²¹ The enthusiasm for ancient Chinese Buddhism in the United States and Europe continued to grow and continued into the 1920s, as Taki Seiichi (1873-1945) said: "When I went there before, I learned that the interest of Europeans in Chinese relics was gradually increasing, and I felt that Chinese relics were more sought after than Japanese relics, this is still the case today. It is not only in Europe but also in the United States."²² In addition, American collectors and curators still tend to uphold Japanese and Western traditional art collections until the 1930s and 1940s.

The concept of collecting Chinese Buddhist stone statues in American museums is also reflected in the reception the statues receive. The change in placement and the American cultural context have given the American collection of Chinese Buddhist stone statues new functions and modes of reception. The main function of Chinese Buddhist stone statues in American museums shifted from missionary to aesthetic and research. The original statues, which were objects of Buddhist worship, became aesthetic statues in museums reflecting the solemn beauty of Eastern Buddhist art and Buddhist philosophies. There is a positive view of Chinese Buddhist stone statues under the influence of traditional Western sculptural art appreciation, unlike the appreciation of Chinese literati paintings and calligraphy in American museums. The change reflects the early

understanding of traditional Chinese art collections in the United States; it is clear that the foresight and vision of collectors and visitors influenced the collection and acceptance of Chinese Buddhist stone statues. Since the late nineteenth century, Chinese Buddhist stone statues have continued to circulate in the United States at a time when the United States, as the world's largest immigrant nation, was experiencing a period of religious and cultural pluralism which the collection's Chinese Buddhist statues served.

4. Elegance on the Stone: Research on Chinese Buddhist Stone Statues in American Collections in Overseas Sinology Circles in the Twentieth Century

In the twentieth century, along with a large number of Chinese Buddhist statues lost, Chinese and foreign scholars mainly carried out a basic description, identification, research, and digitalization of Chinese Buddhist statues collected overseas. Compared with domestic experts who are good at the identification of statues, overseas countries pay more attention to the study of statue style and circulation.

In the 1910s, foreign scholars turned from East Asian art to Chinese art collection and research and began to use modern academic concepts to use the representative Chinese Buddhist stone sculptures that had been lost overseas as supporting materials for the study of Chinese Buddhist art elements, types, forms, and styles. It was the shift from the style of the times and the style of the nation to the study of the style and relationship of regional imagery, as evidenced in the research by well-known scholars Fenollosa, Osvald Sirén (1879-1966), and Matsubara Saburo (1918-1999). Some museums in the United States that collect Chinese Buddhist statues, such as the Metropolitan Museum of Art in New York City, have published books on Chinese sculpture collections, but most museums rarely have complete catalogs of Chinese Buddhist statues.

Research on the diaspora of Chinese art in American collections mainly focuses on the collections of museums and collectors overseas, and the art activities of several important American East Asian art curators and antique dealers, which involve Buddhist stone carvings and statues. There is a lack of research on the circulation chain of the differences between Chinese and American heterogeneous cultures; domestic scholars have not paid attention to the collectors and curators who lead the collections of American museums until this century.

In 1929, Benjamin Franklin March Jr. (1899-1934), director of the department of Asian Art at the Detroit Institute of Art, listed forty-one important Chinese and

Japanese artworks in American museums in the book *China and Japan in Our Museums*. It divides the collection history of Chinese and Japanese art in the United States into four periods: the first period is the collection of small antiques by New England merchant adventurers in the first half of the nineteenth century, the second is Chinese porcelain that sparked interest, the third is the last quarter of the nineteenth century when Japanese art dominated, and the fourth is the current period, roughly in sync with the twentieth century, with a special focus on Chinese art as a whole, accelerated since the Revolution of 1911.²³ Later, the Seattle Art Museum and the Asian Art Museum of San Francisco also collected a large number of Chinese Buddhist art collections.

A Study of Okakura Tenshin's *Comparative Cultural History - Activities and Artistic Thought in Boston*, written by Shimizu Emiko, described Okakura Tenshin's East Asian art activities in Boston. *Relics of Ancient China from the Collection of Dr. Paul Singer* written by Max Loehr (1903-1988), and *Chinese, Korean, and Japanese Sculpture: the Avery Brundage Collection, Asian Art Museum of San Francisco* written by René-Yvon Lefebvre d'Argencé and Diana Turner, talk about the collections of American collectors Paul Singer and Avery Brundage, respectively.

Buddhist statues are also involved in the macroscopic study of the loss of Chinese artworks to American collections. For example, *East Asia Art and American Culture* written by Warren I. Cohen in 1992, describes the story of important American collectors, museum curators, and the process of the loss of several stone statues from the Northern Dynasties of China to the United States, etc. *Yamanaka Shokai: Antique Dealers Who Sell Oriental Treasures to Europe and the United States* written by Kuchiki Yoriko, analyzed the East Asian artworks of antique dealer Yamanaka Sadajiro (1866-1936) with empirical research methods of international transactions, chronicling the ups and downs of the Yamanaka Chamber of Commerce in Japan and the changes in the American art world.

5. Spiritual Connection: Enlightenment from the Collection of Chinese Buddhist Stone Statues

American pioneers and leaders have promoted the collection of Chinese Buddhist stone carvings in American museums with their remarkable philosophy of social and public service, the coexistence of the essence of Eastern and Western art, and the advancement of the human spirit. Eliminating cross-cultural prejudices, research, refinement, dissemination, and promotion of

the essence of human thought and art contributes to the coexistence and development of global multiculturalism.

Based on the characteristics of Chinese Buddhist stone statue collections in American museums, it is clear that style and meaning are core values in the dissemination of Chinese Buddhist stone statues. The missionary Williams first started collecting Buddhist stone statues from the Sui Dynasty of the Northern Dynasties fundamentally because he was familiar with the essence of Buddhist culture due to his Chinese indoctrination, and his collection focused on the connotations of stone statues. Buddhist thought has something in common with Christianity in terms of the inner construction of humanity and is compatible with modern cultural values such as equality and fraternity. Arnold Toynbee points out that charity is the mother of insight, and religion exists to enable human souls to receive the divine light and the essence of religion.²⁴ The style of stone statues of the Northern Qi Dynasty fully expresses the pleasure of introspection. American leaders in the collecting of Chinese Buddhist stone statues separate heterogeneous beliefs from art and understand the value of Chinese Buddhist statues.

The spread of Chinese Buddhist stone statues in China and their collection in the United States were both driven by the needs of the recipient. If the development of Buddhist statues in the Sui Dynasty of the Northern Dynasties was mainly due to the appeal of Buddhism to the Chinese public,²⁵ the collection of Chinese Buddhist stone statues in American museums originated from the existence of art collection needs between private collectors and American museums. In the heterogeneous cultural exchange between China and the West, the art of Chinese Buddhist stone carving statues, represented by the Northern Qi Dynasty statues, has an eternal charm that transcends time and space and connects East and West because of the national style and the meaning of the statues.

The collection and reception of Chinese Buddhist stone statues in American museums illustrate that heterogeneous religious art can be better understood if it fits the inherent pre-defined criteria of the recipient. To enhance the international influence of Chinese culture, it is not only necessary to showcase the unique beauty of traditional Chinese art forms, but also to refine artistic meanings that are based on the inner construction of humanity and have modern values and global significance. It is especially important to note that if there is a corresponding cultural demand from foreign receivers, and the forms and images of artworks are the same and similar to the receivers' foresight and artistic vision, the power and influence of art will be greater and

stronger.

6. Conclusion

American collections of Chinese Buddhist stone statues are dominated by statues of Bodhisattva and Buddha. The main source of the collections are donations and purchases, with most of the statues collected in the 1910s. The identification problems of these statues, which are mainly mixed authenticity, period identification errors, and less geographical identification, are representative of Chinese art collections in American museums in the early twentieth century and typify the shift in focus of American East Asian art collections from Japanese art to Chinese art. The art of Chinese Buddhist iconography tends to move from form, image, and original context to integrated visual culture and cross-cultural exchange studies. Christian culture is the mainstream culture in the United States, but multiple cultures do coexist. The initial collection, the tendency to flourish, and the systematic nature of Chinese Buddhist statuary in American museums are large because the pioneers and leaders of the collections understood Chinese culture, appreciated the distinctive and unique artistic beauty of Chinese Buddhist stone statuary, and understood that the ideas of refinement and introspection contained therein

had something in common with Christian thought and the inner construction of humanity in modernity. As the American civil rights movement promoted equal interaction among all ethnic groups, and religious and cultural identity could transcend ethnic differences, the business and educational activities of American museums had to be integrated with the diverse development of contemporary society, and Chinese Buddhist stone statues became an important part of art collections for their unique artistic and social value.

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美國博物館中國佛教石刻造像流藏探究

劉洪彩

摘要: 佛教石刻造像是美國博物館中國藝術藏品的代表類別。基於調研可知所藏石像，收集來源主要為接受捐贈與購買，20世紀10年代入藏最多，題材主要是菩薩與佛像，偏好北齊造像風格，地域鑒別薄弱，其流藏可分為四個階段，西方與日式美術理念引領美國博物館的中國佛教石像流藏，20世紀海外漢學界的相關研究集中在造像風格與流藏方面，揭示了中國佛教石刻造像藝術因獨特風格與人性內建意蘊而被廣為收藏，異域接受者存在相應文化需求、前見視域存在相通之處則易於接受異質文化。

關鍵詞: 中國；佛教石刻造像；美國博物館；流失；收藏